

Automated pupil image acquisition to estimate serum Vitamin A levels in cattle using pupil color analysis

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Abstract

Japanese black cattle farmers usually decrease cattle serum vitamin A levels during the fattening stage of production to improve beef marbling score. However, such conditioning can negatively impact cattle health and so it is desirable to be able to non-intrusively monitor cattle serum vitamin A level (no blood samples) during this period. The objective of this study is to build an automated system to measure serum vitamin A level by capturing and analyzing the color of cattle pupil images.

The system involves automated image capture of a cattle's pupil, extraction and analysis of the pupil's color (pupil color becomes reddish as the serum vitamin A decreases), and then finally a model estimates vitamin A level based on red and saturation components. The results obtained indicate the system has the potential to rapidly and non-intrusively monitor cattle vitamin A levels in real time.

Background

Japanese black cattle meat is globally renowned for its high quality. To achieve this high quality, marbling is the most influential factor for determining the beef quality grade in the USA, Japan, and Australia (Gotoh *et al.* 2014). The higher the Beef Marbling Standard (BMS) the higher the beef is priced. Thus, ensuring high BMS grades for the meat coming from their cattle is an important issue for cattle-fattening farmers. Research to date has established a direct correlation between vitamin A levels (VA) and BMS: visually assessed marbling scores were higher when cattle VA was low during the fattening period (Kruk *et al.* 2008). In Japan farmers manipulate Japanese black cattle VA to a low level (approximately 30 IU/dL) when the cattle are aged 16-24 months (Fig. 1) to raise beef BMS (Oka *et al.* 1998). For VA, 1IU is the biological equivalent of 0.3µg retinal, or 0.6µg beta-carotene. (Provided by Hyogo Prefectural Hokubu Agricultural Institute)

Figure 1. Ideal serum VA level in cattle during the fattening stage. The vitamin A 30IU/dL line indicates the minimum desired level of VA in Japanese black cattle.

However, such a low VA has the potential to deleteriously impact cattle health, for example nyctalopia, lacrimation and so on (O'Donoghue, 1955). Needless to say, the loss of cattle health can incur severe financial loss for the farmer; up to 1 million JPY. Hence, it is important for farmers to monitor the level of VA. Currently, the standard practice is to perform intrusive, time-consuming (at least 10 days) and expensive (2,000 JPY per assay) blood assays; not to mention being stressful for the cattle and imposing laborious work on the farmer. Thus, an alternative system which can non-intrusively monitor cattle VA would contribute to more efficient and better control of VA, as well as reducing stress and ensuring cattle health during the fattening period.

Numerous reports have shown a linkage between VA levels and mammal eye characteristics. It has been reported that the papilledema, the edema of the optic nerve, provides the first objective signal of changes occurring to the optic disc as a result of low VA (Donkersgoed *et al.* 1988). Such a response has also been demonstrated in Japanese Black cattle using a converted video camera (Fukushima *et al.* 2014). VA levels not only influence the optic nerve, but also the retina: low VA levels in cattle result in retinal degeneration that can lead to increased tapetal reflection and loss of pigmentation of the non-tapetal fundus (Gelatt *et al.*, Moore, 1941). To date though, most of these studies have required the restraint of cattle, and in some cases veterinary administration of mydriasis in the cattle's eye. This is not only stressful on the cattle, it also has the potential for obscuring results as VA is believed to decline as a result of the stress, or while being restrained (Adachi *et al.*, 1998). Initial research by our group (Han *et al.* 2013) using a hand held camera has demonstrated a correlation between VA and eye color opening up the opportunity for a non-intrusive monitoring of cattle VA, which would avoid this stress. Therefore, the objective of this study is to develop a simple and non-stressful method for estimating serum VA levels by analysing the color of automatically captured images of the cattle's pupil.

Methods

This experiment used 24 Japanese black cattle, which were fattened at Hyogo Prefectural Hokubu Agricultural Institute, Japan when the cattle were 10 to 30 months old. The cattle used in this experiment came from the same inbred line "Nishisugidoi" and "Terutatidoi". Before fattening, their average VA level was around 100 IU/dL, and the lowest value during fattening was 9.17 IU/dL. As a standard VA levels in the blood were determined by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC).

Figure 2. Experimental devices

The devices we used are shown in Fig.2. This automatic image acquisition system was set up at the drinking trough in the cattle stall. It was composed of a photographic system, which includes two cameras for left and right eyes, an identification (ID) camera, adjustable lighting and a water system, which includes a flow meter sensor and water cup. When the flow meter sensor detects water decline and the distance sensor detects that there is an object between two cameras the camera began capturing, one camera which has a Polarization (PL) filter and LED with PL film will take several pictures of the cattle's eyes. The PL filter and PL film were added to reduce halation caused by

specular reflection. The distance sensor was combined with adjustable lighting to maintain object illumination at 1200 lx. Each cattle wears a neckband with a different pattern block on it for individual cattle identification. The ID camera, which was set on the top of drinking trough was used to take images of the cattle neckband to identify the cattle.

An automatic Pupil extraction program was developed in Python and the images were processed with OpenCV. The automatic image extraction has two main processes. Firstly, to select out high quality images from all the images taken by the devices. Secondly, to extract the pupil area from the original image and then to retrieve information from this area.

Fig.3 (a) is an example of an original image which was taken by the automatic image acquisition system. This is considered an example of a high quality image. The program changes the RGB image into the HSV space then separates out the H, S, V values. The definition of a high quality image is based on these H, S and V values.

Figure 3. Processes to extract pupil area

Firstly, high quality images should have been selected under stable light conditions. The program skips images with V mean values bigger than 150 or less than 60. Secondly, high quality images should include the cattle's eye. So the program select pixels, omitting H values between 100~160. Fig.3 (b) is one of the images selected for the H image. Fig.3 (c) is an image after noise reduction and Fig.3 (b) after being binarized. In Fig.3 (d) the nearest ellipse of the biggest area in Fig.3 (c) is identified. Fig.3 (e) uses Fig.3 (d) to mask Fig.3 (a), if the ellipse area is bigger than 12080 pixels, this is considered to be an eye image. This image was then processed for pupil color analysis. The color of the pupil was investigated in terms of the Red, Green and Blue (*R*, *B*, *G*) components. The red component ratio, *r* was calculated by the formula:

$$r=R/(R+G+B)$$

Results

The color of pupil and VA

When serum VA levels decreased, the red color component value increased. It shows a negative correlation. This tendency was based on 8 cattle's average results in 2015. As shown in Fig. 4(a), using the selected images the correlation between the red component ratio and serum VA level ranges from 29.11 IU/dL to 68.5 IU/dL.

The time-series data of 8 cattle is shown in Fig. 4(b). This indicates that when VA decreases, *r* increases. In this graph *r* is the monthly average of the 8 cattle. Only the average serum VA level on 4th August, 2015 was under 30 IU/dL. In the subsequent dates, levels of serum VA were around or higher than 30 IU/dL. The negative correlation between *r* and serum VA was apparent during the period with low VA levels; at anyone sampling date when variation in VA levels were small, variation in *r* were also small.

Figure 4. Relationship between red component ratio and vitamin A

Result of Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) Analysis

To estimate VA levels, a MLR model of VA and influential factors was developed in IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0. Thirty factors were used to find the appropriate number of important factors to build the regression model based on statistical analysis.

They are mean, standard deviation and variable values of each channel in the RGB, HSV and L*a*b color space, red component ratio, blue component ratio and time of image capture. The six most important predictor factors were red component ratio, mean value of saturation in HSV, standard deviation value of red in RGB, mean value of brightness in HSV, standard deviation value of a in L*a*b and time of image capture. The results are shown in Table 1. The R² of this MLR model is 0.64. The estimation results are show in Fig. 5. The data are evenly distributed around the regression line, but at low VA levels the results are more random.

Table 1. Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	36.846	6.197		5.946	0.000
	r ratio	-115.543	14.992	-0.327	-7.707	0.000
	sat_mean	0.089	0.020	0.236	4.496	0.000
	red_std	2.085	0.102	0.487	20.462	0.000
	val_mean	0.143	0.026	0.125	5.590	0.000
	time	2.965E-005	0.000	0.068	3.922	0.000

Discussion

The results showed that the pupils of cattle with low VA levels have a higher red component value. Image quality was influenced by many factors related to cattle and environment effects. To effectively estimate serum vitamin A levels calibrated images which reduce these influences, as well as other pupil symptom factors, such as pupillary light reflex and surface reflection (symptoms reported to be associated with low serum VA levels) needed to be taken into account to improve the accuracy of the model.

Figure 5. Measured and predicted VA by MLR estimation model

Conclusions

A non-intrusive, automatic image acquisition and analysis system to predict serum vitamin A level in Japanese black cattle has been presented. A negative correlation between the red component ratio of the cattle's pupil and their VA levels were obtained in 2015 from automatically captured pupil images. Subsequent image analysis using multiple linear regression analysis identified 6 important factors linking pupil characteristics with VA level. An estimation model based on these factors, while not yet providing an accurate estimation of VA, points to the possibility of estimating serum vitamin A level using this automatic system. It should be noted that this model may not be applicable to other cattle breeds.

Acknowledgments

This study was supported by JSPS KAKENHI Grant Number JP26252044. We also wish to express our gratitude to the staff of Hyogo Prefectural Agricultural Institute and Kyoto University Farm. We really appreciate Professor Ferruccio Giaretta and other laboratory members for their kind help during the experiment, and Professor Garry Piller for his proof reading and valuable suggestions for this study.

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